

BENEFITS AND DRAWBACKS OF USING DIGITAL ASSESSMENT IN LEARNING ENGLISH: STUDENTS’ PERCEPTION

Ardiana, S.Pd., M.Pd.
Haerani
Nurul Aini Islamiah
Shela Aulia
Shomukhammadov Kholiddin

Corresponding author’s email: ardiana@unismuh.ac.id

^{1,2,3,4} English Education Study Program, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Muhammadiyah University of Makassar, Indonesia

Address: Sultan Alauddin Street 259, Makassar City, South Sulawesi Province, Indonesia, 90221, +62 852-9933-4566

*⁵Department of integrated course of English №3
Kichik Halka Street, G9a avenue, 21a, Tshkent City, Uzbekistan*

Abstract: The purpose of this study isto determine the students' perceptions regarding the benefits and drawbacks of utilizing digital assessments such as Kahoot and Quizizz in English classrooms. This study employs a qualitative approach, employing interviews as the primary method for collecting data. The participants of this study were 15 students majoring in English education at Muhammadiyah University of Makassar who had experienced using Kahoot and Quizizz as tools for learning English. Researchers conducted interviews to gather student perspectives and discovered that students believe that using Kahoot and Quizizz offers several advantages. These include convenient accessibility, engaging features, immediate feedback, and enhanced critical thinking, and memory abilities. However, students also mentioned challenges such as technical issues and limited time for completing the questions. The implementation of Kahoot and Quizizz as digital evaluation tools yielded highly favorable outcomes according to students' perspectives

Keywords: students’ perception, digital assessment, learning English

INTRODUCTION

The use of digital resources into educational settings has revolutionized the traditional methods of teaching. An important component of this change is the use of digital assessments, such as Quizizz and Kahoot, to boost language learning experiences in the classroom. Within the field of English language education, the utilization of these platforms has attracted attention due to its capacity to actively involve students and facilitate interactive learning.

The challenge of identifying suitable evaluation techniques for young language learners is arduous because of their restricted capacity for sustained focus, underdeveloped ability for abstract reasoning, and the requirement for tangible, stimulating material. Digital learning as the use of digital media (such as texts or pictures) delivered through the Internet. The purpose of this form of learning is to enhance learners' knowledge and skills, as well as improve teaching effectiveness. In addition, the utilisation of digital assessment significantly aids in decreasing paper consumption. According to (Alruwais, 2018), the advantages of digital assessment can be classified into four perspectives: students, teachers, institutions, and educational objectives. Students like online assessment due to the autonomy it provides in their studies, the familiarity they have with the platform, and its resemblance to recreational activities, such as games or simulations. Utilising paper-based tests requires a significant amount of time to evaluate and grade each individual paper. In contrast, implementing E-assessment methods will effectively reduce the time burden on teachers. Additional advantages of utilizing these digital exams have been unveiled by specialists and academics. A key benefit of digital assessment is its ability to enhance learner engagement in the assessment process. Furthermore, digital assessment offers expeditious and precise feedback, enabling teachers to save time on grading while allowing students to promptly access their scores upon completion of assignments or exams (Syahria, 2019; Alruwais, 2018; Sahidu, Gunawan, Suranti, & Nisrina, 2020). Student values, along with their corresponding statistics, can be automatically maintained on the website as a teacher archive, alleviating concerns about potential loss of students' grade data.

This method of evaluating online exams digitally can be implemented using an existing internet-based application that is freely accessible. Kahoot and Quizizz are among such applications. Both of these web-based apps primarily provide online test authoring capabilities, encompassing a range of test formats, including multiple choice and true/false. Both of these types of applications offer several benefits, including a wide range of useful features. One notable advantage is the incorporation of gamification components, which are simple to integrate and enhance student engagement and enjoyment (Tenau, Anissa, & Widyaningrum, 2019; Ismail & Mohammad, 2017). Heinzen (2014) suggests that students generally appreciate receiving tests, but the specific format and structure of the test can impact their performance. Therefore, incorporating gamification into assessments can offer a more enjoyable alternative.

As the rapid advancement of education into the digital domain, technology has become omnipresent in classrooms around the globe. Although the act of incorporating technology into the classroom has grown widespread, it is insufficient to guarantee student engagement and satisfactory learning outcomes (Khan, Egbue, Palkie & Madden, 2017). Hence, educators require efficient tools and tactics that can enhance motivation and facilitate student learning. One of the available tools is Quizizz. Quizizz is specifically created to enhance teachers' ability to create an engaging and enjoyable learning atmosphere, while also providing students with a more captivating and less monotonous

approach to learning (Degirmenci, 2021). It can be utilized for formative evaluations, such as Quizizz that measure student progress throughout a course, or summative assessments, such as Quizizz that evaluate student proficiency in a subject. This application possesses numerous distinctive and appealing attributes that cater to the needs of both students and teachers, rendering it highly desirable for utilization (Muji, Ambiyar, Aziz & Hidayat, 2021). These characteristics encompass the capacity to effortlessly and expeditiously generate quizzes, offer instantaneous feedback, and tailor quizzes to individual learning requirements. Furthermore, Quizizz incorporates a leader-board functionality that enables students to engage in quiz competitions, enhancing their motivation and participation in the learning process.

With the fast integration of education into the digital realm, technology has become ubiquitous in classrooms worldwide. While the use of technology in the classroom has become common, it alone is not enough to ensure student engagement and successful learning results. Kahoot! are used to assess student progress throughout a course, or to test student expertise in a subject through quizzes. Kahoot! is a gamified platform that includes quizzes, chats, and surveys. KAHOOT! is a cost-free educational platform that uses game-based learning to engage educators from many subjects. It provides an interactive and captivating method for learning (Academy, 2016). Kahoot! possesses distinctive attributes that are characteristic of both gaming and educational models. Kahoot! is an interactive educational platform that allows students to participate in learning activities in an enjoyable and competitive way.

This paper investigates students' perspectives on the utilization of digital assessment tools, notably Quizizz and Kahoot, for the purpose of acquiring English language skills in an educational setting. Through an exploration of the personal experiences of students, our objective is to reveal valuable information regarding the efficiency, difficulties, and overall influence of integrating these digital assessment techniques into language teaching. Gaining insight into students' viewpoints on these technologies is essential for both educators and the relationship between technology and language acquisition in modern educational settings.

METHOD

This research is qualitative, and the subject of this research is a student majoring in English education at the Muhammadiyah University of Makassar. According to Moleong (2012), qualitative research is a method of research that produces data in the form of words, both spoken and written, about the individuals and their observed behavior. The subjects were 15 students of Muhammadiyah University of Makassar. These students have been accustomed to using Kahoot and Quizizz applications in English learning. Data collection was carried out through interviews. Researchers asked 20 questions to identify students' perceptions of the benefits and drawbacks of using the Kahoot and Quizizz applications for learning English. The interview data were then transcribed and analyzed to find relevant data needed before finally being displayed and drawn as a conclusion.

RESULTS

There are some perceptions of Students' using Kahoot and Quizizz in Learning English based on the interview that have been conducted, that is:

Benefits of Using Digital Assessment in Learning English:

Convenient Accessibility

Students find convenient accessibility to the Kahoot and Quizizz applications. To make this application convenient and accessible, users only need to have a good internet connection. This is very important to facilitate accessibility in order for students to conveniently participate in answering questions, and see results directly, in addition Internet connection allows real-time content updates. This means educators can easily upload or update Kahoot and Quizizz, keeping learning materials up to date and relevant. In their statement, the student in question states:

“Kahoot and Quizizz are very easy to access and convenient accessibility, we only need to have a good internet connection and we can log in using the official Kahoot and Quizizz application or website.” (Student 09)

Engaging Features

Students find using Kahoot and Quizizz as digital assessments very fun because they have many engaging features, such as : multiple choice, multiplayer mode, picture and sound, etc. Students get excited when playing Kahoot or Quizizz games, which offer leaderboards, personalization options, and quick feedback. For example, the leaderboard function adds a competitive aspect that stimulates competitiveness between students, resulting in a fun learning atmosphere. With a variety of question formats, Quizizz and Kahoot's customizability allows instructors to tailor exams to each student's needs. The instant feedback capabilities of both platforms enhance the learning experience by providing students with instant information to improve their performance and encourage active engagement in a fun and exciting learning process. This can be seen in the statement:

“When I use Kahoot and Quizizz I feel happy doing the assignment because it uses the multiple choice feature with the game system and there is also an opportunity feature to correct our wrong answers.” (Student 10)

“I like it when I'm working on questions with music that calms me and makes me challenged in my work.” (Student 02)

Immediate Feedback

Students feel that using Kahoot and Quizizz provides assignments very effectively because because the feedback from the answers is immediate. When interviewed, students also highlighted that these advantages not only impact process efficiency, but also contribute to environmental sustainability by reducing paper consumption. They consider

that the adaptability of this platform reflects a positive response to technological developments in the educational context, providing a more modern learning experience and in line with the needs of today's digital generation.

"Using the Kahoot and Quizizz applications for giving assignments is very effective because the feedback from the answers is immediate and we also save time without having to write questions and answers on paper. This also saves us paper and minimizes global warming." (Student 10)

Enhanced Critical Thinking and Memory Abilities

Students feel that using Kahoot and Quizizz really helps them understand the material and improve their, think critically and memory abilities. Due to the allotted time feature, these applications pose unique challenges that contribute to increasing understanding of the subject matter. Additionally, these interactive tools stimulate critical thinking and memory abilities, showing a positive correlation between their use and improved cognitive abilities. The ensuing discussion explores the profound impact Kahoot and Quizizz have on students' academic journeys, highlighting the diverse benefits that go beyond the experience of taking a quiz. The statement clearly demonstrates this:

"When I use Kahoot and Quizizz I am challenged in terms of remembering the material and this makes me when I use these applications I become more careful in reading and I also think quickly to catch up on assignment time." (Student 03)

Drawbacks of Using Digital Assessment in Learning English:

Technical issues

The main obstacle expressed in interviews was signal problems or unstable internet connections. If the internet signal is unstable, students express difficulty logging into the platform or even experience problems completing assignments or exams. Students' hopes that signal problems will be resolved quickly reflects the need for reliable technological infrastructure, especially internet signals which can affect the user experience on the platform. The following text is excerpted from the student's interview statement:

"Hopefully it's a signal problem immediately resolved because sometimes we are prevented from entering because of the signal and sometimes when we are doing our work we suddenly leave because of signal problems" (Student 05)

It is also students' aspirations that this system simplification will help students who are using this platform for the first time, to qualify for and can access and operate digital learning tools more easily and efficiently. Students expected that signal problem and the system is simplified for the new students who are the first time using Kahoot and Quizizz. This is contained in the student's statement interviewed:

"The system is simplified for the new students who have never face the digital assessment" (Student 07)

Limited Time for Completing the Questions

Students feel that working on questions on Kahoot and Quizizz is very limited as many students run out of time to answer questions. In the Kahoot and Quizizz applications there is a limited time for completing the questions. Although the limited time for completing the questions is designed to increase intensity and challenge, the impact can be significant. Some students stated that they needed more time to answer questions on Kahoot and Quizizz which made it possible for students to experience obstacles due to rushing to answer within the allotted time. This can increase stress and tension levels during learning sessions, affecting students' concentration and focus. The following statement demonstrates this point:

"Sometimes the scores I get are low because of the limited time I have when doing assignments and that makes me feel a little disappointed." (Student 01)

DISCUSSION

Student perspectives on the benefits of using digital assessments.

Based on the results of interviews with English Language Education students, researchers found that Kahoot and Quizizz are applications with convenient accessibility. There are a lot of students who choose to use the Quizizz and Kahoot applications as digital assessment tools. Which suggests that the accessibility of quiz applications such as Quizizz and Kahoot are key factors for high user engagement. This reveals that Kahoot and Quizizz are digital assessment applications that are very familiar among students, especially English language education students. Apart from that, researchers also found that many students highly recommend using the Kahoot and Quizizz applications because these applications have various interesting and fun features. Students also like the Kahoot and Quizizz applications as digital assessment applications because the feedback from Kahoot and Quizizz is very fast. This is in line with Wibowo (2021), who stated that students appreciate the flexibility and direct feedback from online assessments. Researchers also found that many students think that using the Kahoot and Quizizz applications is very effective and very helpful in understanding the material and improving their reading skills, thinking critically and quickly, listening carefully, and remembering. This is consistent with the findings of study conducted by Sofyan (2020) who stated in their research that the use of Kahoot and Quizizz was proven to significantly increase understanding of the material, improve critical thinking, and memory skills.

Student perspectives on the drawbacks of using digital assessments.

Based on the results of interviews with English Language Education students, researchers found that several students stated that when they used or accessed Kahoot and Quizizz, they had network problems. In accordance with the findings of earlier studies, this is the case (Chiang, 2020; Saracoglu & Kocabatmaz, 2019; Wang & Tahir, 2020) that revealed significant challenges that impact the overall learning experience,

and the main challenges revolve around internet connectivity issues, as reported in previous studies. It is important to note that these technical issues are often due to internet availability and not inherent weaknesses in the platform, thus highlighting the persistent nature of internet-related challenges. Apart from that, researchers also found that students thought that there was very little time when completing assignments, which made them very rushed to complete the questions given. This seems to be consistent with the viewpoint of Wang (2015), who said in the results of his research that students felt rushed and experienced increased levels of stress during work due to limited time. This is an external weakness of the Kahoot and Quizizz applications, which students can avoid by paying close attention to the questions.

CONCLUSION

From the results of research regarding student perspectives regarding the benefits and drawbacks of using the Kahoot and Quizizz applications in learning English, researchers found that they obtained more and more positive perceptions from students, such as very easy accessibility, interesting features, fast feedback, and improving critical thinking, reading, listening, and memory skills. However, there were several shortcomings that researchers encountered when interviewing students, such as network problems when accessing Kahoot and Quizizz as well as problems regarding limited time when doing assignments on the Kahoot and Quizizz applications. apart from the technicalities of the Kahoot and Quizizz applications.

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